

Gall midge damage at rice panicle stage

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Gall midge damage to rice panicles and spikelets was first recorded at Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, during 1974 and 1978 kharif. In 1982 kharif, panicles and spikelets of 153 late transplanted tall and semi-dwarf popular varieties were seriously damaged by gall midge. We began varietal screening to isolate a source of gall midge resistance and to identify damage symptoms.

Two rows of 18 hills of each variety screened were transplanted 23 Aug 1982. Hills with panicle infestation, infested panicles, infested spikelets, and healthy panicles were recorded (Table 1). About 37% of hills, 21% of panicles, and 0.4% of spikelets were infested.

Of varieties screened for resistance, only Madhuri, Phalgun, and Surekha did not have gall midge-infested panicles or spikelets in all three plantings (Table 2). However, Madhuri was highly susceptible to gall midge at tillering stage. All hills of local tall varieties Safri 17, Basmati

Table 1. Gall midge damage to panicles and spikelets in staggered plantings, 1982 kharif, Raipur, India.

Sowing date	Varieties planted (no.)	Hills (no.)	Panicles (no.)	Infestation (%)		
				Hill	Panicle	Spikelet
22 Jun	146	2,971	14,845	34	16	0.6
12 Jul	153	5,436	29,686	37	17	0.3
5 Aug	81	1,862	7,690	41	29	0.3
Mean				37	21	0.4

370, Khao Dawk Mali, and Rati were infested.

Panicles and spikelets of varieties resistant to gall midge at vegetative stage showed varying degrees of susceptibility (Table 2).

We described the damage symptoms. The flag-leaf sheath is distorted, twisted, and crinkled with blunt or curved tips, atrophied or without leaf blade, and tissue paper thin. The penultimate leaf suppresses the flag leaf sheath and falsely represents the flag leaf. It tightly entangles the flag leaf, inhibits panicle exertion, and prevents spikelet fertilization to varying degrees. Levels of sterility in susceptible Bd 200 varied from 53% to 62%. □

Table 2. Gall midge damage to panicles and spikelets of midge-resistant varieties.

Variety	Infestation (%)		
	Hill	Panicle	Spikelet
R2384 (R68-1/Jaya)	1.0	1.0	0.0
R35-2752 (IR22/W1263)	7.0	1.0	0.0
R35-2750 (IR22/W1263)	6.0	1.0	0.0
Siam 29	21.0	12.0	1.0
Bangoli-5 (RPW6-17)	19.0	9.0	1.0
Mean	11.0	5.0	0.3

Pest management and control WEEDS

Tolerance of rice weeds for natural floodwater submergence

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We studied the effect of natural floodwater on growth of dryland and wetland rice weeds.

During early Sep 1982, much of the AAI farm was flooded by river water. After floodwater receded, weed growth on dryland and wetland rice fields was observed. Ten random samples of each weed species on the farm were observed and growth stage, plant height, and nature of submergence were recorded.

In dryland rice fields, which had 60 cm floodwater for 3 days, 13 weed

Table 1. Effect of submergence in 60cm floodwater depth for 3 days on dryland rice weeds.

Weed species	Growth stage	Plant height (cm)	Nature of submergence	Remarks
Broadleaf weeds				
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex. Roth	Flowering	21	Submerged	Unaffected
<i>Biophytum sensitivum</i> (L.) Dc.	Vegetative	5	- do -	- do -
<i>B. sensitivum</i> (L.) Dc.	Flowering	8	- do -	- do -
<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Fruiting	95	Partially submerged	Complete defoliation and death of the plant
Convolvulus arvensis L.				
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Vegetative	16	Submerged	Unaffected
<i>Lindernia Ciliata</i> (Colsm.) Penn.	Flowering	26	- do -	- do -
<i>Lindernia crustacea</i> (L.) F. Muell.	Vegetative	6	- do -	- do -
<i>Oldenlandia corymbosa</i> L.	Vegetative	6	- do -	- do -
<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Vegetative	12	- do -	- do -
<i>Phyllanthus urinaria</i> L.	Fruiting	51	- do -	- do -
	Fruiting	75	Partially submerged	- do -

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species were unaffected by submergence. *Cleome viscosa* L. was defoliated and died although it was only partially submerged (Table 1).

In wetland fields with 90 cm floodwater for 4 days, 6 species were unaffected. *Eclipta prostrata* (L.) L. at vegetative stage was defoliated, except for the terminal leaf. It later recovered from flooding. Submergence at flowering stage did not damage it (Table 2). □

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Weed species	Growth stage	Plant height (cm)	Nature of submergence	Remarks
Grasses				
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Vegetative	10	Submerged	- do -
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Flowering	28	- do -	- do -
<i>Panicum trypheron</i> Schult.	Flowering	35	-do-	- do -
Sedge				
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Flowering	18	-do-	-do-

Table 2. Effect of complete submergence in 90-cm floodwater depth for 4 days on wetland rice weeds.

Weed species	Growth stage	Plant height (cm)	Remarks
Broadleaf weeds			
<i>Altemanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex. Roth	Flowering	19	Unaffected
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Vegetative	18	- do -
<i>Caesulia axillaris</i> Roxb.	Vegetative	25	- do -
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Vegetative	20	Defoliation of all leaves except terminal leaf
<i>E. prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Flowering	29	Unaffected
Grasses			
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Flowering	65	- do -
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. var. <i>brevisetata</i> (Doell) Nelr.	Flowering	80	- do -
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. var. <i>crus-galli</i>	Vegetative	57	- do -
Sedge			
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Vegetative	45	- do -

Pest management and control NEMATODES

Nematode pests associated with deep water rice in Bangladesh

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Ufra disease caused by *Ditylenchus angustus* (Butler, 1913) Filipjev, 1936. Experiments at Matlab Bazar, Comilla, in 1980 and 1981 showed that delayed sowing or, even better, transplanting of deepwater (floating) rice reduced ufra disease incidence and produced higher yields than when standard practice was

followed. In 1982, treatment with the nematicide carbofuran was tried with delayed planting. Transplanting in late Apr successfully established the crop and also reduced ufra disease incidence. Applying 1.5 kg carbofuran ai/ha further reduced the disease (see table). Larger scale testing of the technique is planned for 1983.

Disease resurgence has been monitored since its setback by the 1979 drought. In most of the known ufra areas, disease incidence has stabilized. In some areas, however, disease severity has lessened, which may be related to the adoption of deepwater rice - boro - deep-

water rice cultivation.

Of 600 entries screened for ufra resistance in the deepwater tank, 85 were found highly resistant. In a pot screening test of 101 of the IRDWON II and III breeding series, 6 entries had no visible infestation and 6 had less than 10% infestation. Forty-seven entries from the 1981 screening were field tested, but disease incidence was too low for satisfactory results. Ten 1981 entries have been highly resistant in all tests.

Root-knot disease caused by *Meloidogyne graminicola* (Golden & Birchfield, 1965) Dry season populations of *M. graminicola*